

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Abubaker

FIRST NAME: Arwa

PROGRAM CODE: DIPH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: One

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with the page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2021, 13-14)
2. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 29-30)
3. Plagiarism: Is it Avoidable? (EUCLID 2021, 35)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 41)
5. Tips When Correcting Papers (EUCLID 2021, 66-71)

OVERVIEW OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

One of the most important things I took away from the period one course is that academic writing is a never-ending process, and there is always more to learn. The information is extremely structured and well-organized, which piques your interest in learning and encourages participation.

I am reflecting on five key ideas that I found to be the most helpful in this paper despite my extreme hesitance to write the first response paper.

2)SOME RULES OF THUMPS FOR WRITING A PAPER

It would be ideal to start your work with a clear statement of your argument in the opening paragraph. When faced with a plethora of ideas, attempt to maintain focus, adhere strictly to the objectives of your studies, be as explicit as you can, and steer clear of generalizations (EUCLID 2021,13).

When it comes to academic writing, conciseness is essential. Avoid using large words and paragraphs and speak to the reader in the clearest possible way. If word and style repetition is not avoided, readers may become easily disinterested. However, provide evidence for your claim by highlighting pertinent paragraphs; try to avoid using quotations unless absolutely necessary (EUCLID 2021, 13).

Make sure you critique your own argument before criticizing another person's work or pointing out where your argument falls short. To feel good about your paper, you must write it and modify it several times. However, reading your work aloud will help you see your errors more clearly (EUCLID 2021, 14).

There are always guidelines available for practice, and patience is needed for repetitions, which are necessary for practice.

3) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

It is important to know the distinctions between American and British English, but practicing it might be challenging if, like me, English is not your first language.

In my native Sudan, schools spoke British English, but because America has such a strong effect on many facets of daily life, I am sure I developed a hybrid language.

It was encouraging to learn that the variations extend beyond variations in spelling, grammar, and pronunciation to include variations in punctuation usage in general, date writing, equality vocabulary, and politically correct references (EUCLID 2021, 29).

Despite the fact that it is widespread influence, American English has been influenced by Yiddish and Ethnic Jewish culture, both lexically and structurally, in contrast to British English (EUCLID 2021, 30).

4) PLAGIARISM: IS IT AVOIDABLE

When a writer borrows a source of information without providing credit to the source's originator, it is considered plagiarism, whether intentionally or unintentionally.

Acknowledging the source of knowledge is important since doing so might be interpreted as stolen intellectual property or unethical effort exploitation.

The secret to preventing plagiarism is citation; aside from general information that may be found in a variety of sources, the writer must credit any words or ideas that they have taken verbatim from other people.

The two parts of citations are work listed and in-text citations. Whether it is a quotation or paraphrase (short or big sentence), the citation will be simple if you follow the institution's specifications (EUCLID 2021, 35).

5) STYLE GUIDE

The style guide is the greatest tool to employ in an author's daily work for the following reasons: consistency, coherence, time and effort savings, and representing the publication authority identity or style rather than the writer's style.

What, then, is a guide to style? A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent, according to the definition provided in the EUCLID course pack.

Since the style guide serves as a reference for producing documentation, it covers a wide range of topics, from the overall structure of the content to the minute minutiae of symbol usage.

You must ascertain your institution's preferences in order to select the appropriate style guide. EUCLID, for instance, suggests the Chicago Rules (Turabian) and American English writing style; however, other options are also acceptable (EUCLID 2021, 41).

Despite the fact that style guides are typically connected to particular kinds of writing, I believe they are a useful tool for authors across all genres.

6) TIPS WHEN CORRECTING A PAPER

The final portion of the course pack, which focused on example paper revisions, taught me a lot. It was immediately apparent to me after reading it that it would give me more confidence while writing the answer paper and also give me practical assistance in operationalizing the theoretical information.

Even if the paper was your own, begin editing it by focusing on its overall appearance. Does the paper appear well-structured and shaped? Next, adhere to the institute's guidelines for style guide usage and revision. examining in-depth information on headings, word counts, font size, etc. (EUCLID 2021, 66).

Writing requires precise punctuation and capitalization, and many authors—including myself—are prone to making these simple errors. Avoid word abbreviations, though, such as "it's supposed to write it is," as they look informal. Instead, always attempt to write words in their whole. Additionally, it is advised to write concisely wherever feasible—using fewer words while conveying the same ideas (EUCLID 2021, 68).

Check your institute's reference preferences and do your best to adhere to them, as references can be a rich source of errors. Recognizing the distinctions between referring books, videos, and papers, as well as dictionaries (EUCLID 2021, 71).

7)CONCLUSION

Acquiring knowledge and enhancing academic writing is a drawn-out yet rewarding process that calls for perseverance and dedication. Additionally, you must approach the process methodically and with guidance. With EUCLID, I believe I am headed in the correct direction.

REFERENCES

Cleenerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.